

Using third-party telemetry data to inform wildlife management

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Project Objectives

The first meeting of this working group discovered that more than half of all animal telemetry projects undertaken in Australasia between 2000 and 2013 remain unpublished and inaccessible to the wider ecological community (Report 1).

A principal of ACEAS is to 'facilitate the advancement of ecosystem knowledge through the search for patterns and principles in existing data'. In this second workshop, we undertook a project to ascertain if animal telemetry data collected by a third party (or parties) could be collated and modelled to synthesise a product useful for wildlife management.

To undertake this task, locations from GPS-collared feral cats were obtained from an online public archive dedicated to animal telemetry data (OzTrack.org). The telemetry data was provided by Arid Recovery, an ecosystem restoration initiative dedicated to the restoration of Australia's arid lands (<http://www.aridrecovery.org.au/>). The organisation has had limited success with small mammal reintroductions due to the presence of feral cats and had initially tagged the feral cats in an attempt to improve efficiency in the control of these pests.

Our objective was to use the cat telemetry location data collected by Arid Recovery to provide information that would assist in controlling the number of feral cats, and identify potentially safe areas for the reintroduction of native small mammals. In doing so, the group assessed the challenges faced when re-using animal telemetry data, collected by a third party, for ecological analysis and synthesis.

Methods

1. Obtain third-party collected GPS-based animal telemetry data through an online data-repository.
2. Convert animal location data into information from which a measure of ecological analysis and synthesis could be achieved.
3. Obtain environmental data for the area from which the animal telemetry data was collected. These data files were open-source and accessible via an online repository (TERN data discovery portal). Layers were obtained for Persistent Green-Vegetation Fraction and Wooded Mask (Landsat, AusCover) as well as raster layers based upon Euclidean distance to permanent water bodies, creek lines, and roads in the landscape (Figure 1).
4. Identify the environmental features associated with the presence of feral cats and predict the probability of cat presence throughout the landscape-based open their association with environmental variables using the maximum entropy method.

Major Challenges

1. The re-use of animal telemetry location data collected by a third party was challenging due to the question specific context of the original study. This will be a persistent issue in the re-use of animal telemetry location data but can be overcome by the relative meta-data.
2. Locating the necessary environmental data for the study area was challenging. TERN/ACEAS staff were of great assistance in obtaining these data. Improved cataloguing within the TERN Data Discovery Portal since this study has greatly improved data discovery.
3. Animal location telemetry data results in repeated measures from the same individual, and therefore suffers from non-independence. This issue was addressed in this study by producing a probability density distribution map of cat presence from the cat trajectory between location fixes (Figure 2). Using these data produced a model of good fit (Table 1).

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Major Findings

Permanent water bodies were associated with a high probability of cat presence, followed by vegetation cover. Roads and creek lines did not have a significant influence upon cat presence (Table 2). Extrapolation of the model over a wider area (up to 100 km) illustrated localities with a high and low potential for cat presence (Figure 3).

Key papers or products

The findings from the study will be used by Arid Recovery to assist in feral cat trapping and shooting programs, and for designating small mammal release areas. The success of this project will be defined by the results on the ground (an increased success in feral cat trapping and successful small mammal reintroductions in designated low cat presence areas).

How will this affect Australian ecosystem science and management?

1. Predation pressure upon native wildlife by feral cats is a problem throughout Australia, and the study findings may assist local authorities in arid regions in managing feral cats.
2. The collection of individual-based animal movement data by telemetry is often expensive and challenging. The re-use of animal telemetry data, collected by a third-party, has the potential to inform and improve management for little additional cost (see report 1).
3. The field of animal telemetry suffers from data-hoarding. Practitioners are cautious in sharing their data for fear of others publishing their ideas (although as a group we were unable to identify a single case of this ever happening). Increased value placed upon the re-use of animal telemetry data will hopefully encourage others to allow access to their archival data for re-use by the wider ecological community.

Table 1: Seventy percent of cat location data was used to train the model and 30% was used to test the model. The Area Under the Curve (AUC) result shows the model was a good-fit of the data

	AUC
Training data	0.97
Test data	0.91

Table 2: The MaxENT model results.

Variable	Contribution
Water	63.1
Creeks	11.4
Roads	13.2
Vegetation	22.2

Figure 1: Image matrix showing Arid Recovery measurements from GPS collars attached to fifteen cats whose position was determined every three hours. These data were overlain with spatial information.

Figure 2: Probability distribution of cat presence, calculated from trajectories recorded by GPS-based telemetry (location fixes every 30 min, $n = 13$).

Figure 3: The results from the MaxENT model illustrating the predicted probability of cat occurrence throughout the wider landscape. The black square denotes the area from which cat presence information was collected.